

Densities and viscosities of ternary systems of maltose, alkali metal halides and water from 293.15 to 313.15 K

Reena Gupta and Mukhtar Singh*

Department of Chemistry, Agra College, Agra-282 002, India

Manuscript received 20 May 2003, revised 28 October 2003, accepted 5 February 2004

Densities and viscosities of ternary systems involving maltose, alkali metal halides (NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI) and water have been determined at temperatures : 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. From the density data the values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) of maltose in purely aqueous solutions and also in the presence of NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI have been obtained with a view to determining the partial molar volume of transfer ($V_{2,tr}^0$) of maltose from water to aqueous solutions of NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI. The viscosity data of alkali metal halides in purely aqueous solutions and in the presence of maltose have been analyzed by applying Jones-Dole equation. The structure-making and structure-breaking capacities of NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI in purely aqueous solution and in the presence of maltose have been ascertained from the temperature dependence of V_{ϕ}^0 .

The properties of solutions of polyols and of sugars in aqueous and mixed aqueous solutions are important in many areas of applied chemistry and are essential for understanding the chemistry of biological systems^{1,2}.

However, until recently, there have been comparatively few thermodynamic and other physico-chemical investigations in this field^{2,3}. Polyhydroxy compounds are well known stabilizing agents^{4,5} for the native state of proteins/enzymes but the mechanism of this process is still not clear. Therefore, the data revealing the hydration behavior of these solutes are desirable for better understanding of such processes. Banipal *et al.*⁶ have reported studies on thermodynamic and transport properties in mixed aqueous solutions of urea and sodium chloride at different temperatures. The results of the studies have been discussed in terms of structure-maker and structure-breaker processes.

The volumetric and viscometric studies of electrolytes at infinite dilution in various mixed solvent systems have contributed to our knowledge about electrolyte-non-electrolyte-water interactions. By examining the viscosity B -coefficient and V_{ϕ}^0 of ions as a function of size, nature, temperature and composition of the mixed solvent, it is possible to study the effect of these parameters on ion-water interactions, with the hope of obtaining a better understanding of the interactions in solutions.

Nikam *et al.*⁷ have determined densities of ammonium sulphate, potassium sulphate and aluminium sulphate in aqueous dimethylformamide at different concentrations in the temperature range 298.15 to 313.15 K. From these data

apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}) have been derived and analyzed using Masson equation⁸. The limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and slope (S_v) are interpreted in terms of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions, respectively. The structure making/breaking capacities of electrolytes have been ascertained from the equation of Hepler⁹. Banipal and coworkers¹⁰ have determined apparent molar volumes of some disaccharides in water and in aqueous guanidine hydrochloride solutions at different concentrations and at 298.15 K from density measurements. Partial molar volumes at infinite dilution (V_2^0) determined from V_{ϕ} values, have been utilized to estimate partial molar volumes of transfer $V_{2,tr}^0$ of the disaccharides from water to aqueous guanidine hydrochloride solutions. The $V_{2,tr}^0$ values have been found to be positive for all the disaccharides and increase with the increase in the concentration of the co-solute (guanidine) which suggest that overall structural order is enhanced in aqueous guanidine hydrochloride solutions.

Very recently, Parmar and Dhiman¹¹ have reported studies on the determination of partial molar volumes of some mineral salts from density measurements in aqueous medium at different concentrations and temperatures. The results have been interpreted in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions.

From the above survey of literature it is indicated that partial molar volume and viscosity data give valuable information regarding solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions. This prompted us to undertake the title study in the

* Address for correspondence : HIG-142, Phase A, Shastri Puram, Sikandra, Agra-282 007, India.

Table I. Values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_v) of maltose in aqueous solutions of alkali halides at different temperatures*

Alkali halide	V_{ϕ}^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹) [Alkali halide] (mol dm ⁻³)			S_v (cm ³ dm ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2}) [Alkali halide] (mol dm ⁻³)		
	0.0	0.10	0.50	0.0	0.10	0.50
	Temp. 293.15 K					
NaCl	898.61 (±0.40)	879.04 (±0.10)	785.55 (±0.05)	-564.05 (±0.05)	-564.02 (±0.08)	-462.00 (±0.05)
KCl	898.61 (±0.40)	850.96 (±0.04)	777.69 (±0.01)	-564.05 (±0.05)	-574.44 (±0.06)	-451.07 (±0.03)
KBr	898.61 (±0.40)	837.66 (±0.04)	652.82 (±0.08)	-502.21 (±0.09)	-502.21 (±0.09)	-335.17 (±0.03)
KI	898.61 (±0.40)	829.23 (±0.07)	565.79 (±0.01)	-499.66 (±0.04)	-499.66 (±0.04)	-257.80 (±0.20)
	Temp. 303.15 K					
NaCl	931.11 (±0.09)	904.31 (±0.09)	807.22 (±0.08)	-596.18 (±0.02)	570.68 (±0.02)	-482.38 (±0.02)
KCl	931.11 (±0.09)	910.52 (±0.08)	768.73 (±0.07)	-596.18 (±0.02)	-574.15 (±0.05)	-434.46 (±0.04)
KBr	931.11 (±0.09)	888.85 (±0.02)	670.11 (±0.09)	-596.18 (±0.02)	-559.00 (±0.02)	-351.11 (±0.05)
KI	931.11 (±0.09)	853.78 (±0.02)	570.41 (±0.09)	-596.18 (±0.02)	-522.38 (±0.02)	-255.10 (±0.05)
	Temp. 313.15 K					
NaCl	903.09 (±0.01)	800.52 (±0.08)	789.30 (±0.05)	-566.71 (±0.04)	-452.36 (±0.04)	-459.23 (±0.07)
KCl	903.09 (±0.01)	899.74 (±0.06)	791.77 (±0.03)	-566.71 (±0.04)	-563.31 (±0.04)	-464.36 (±0.04)
KBr	903.09 (±0.01)	858.53 (±0.07)	644.64 (±0.06)	-566.71 (±0.04)	-522.46 (±0.04)	-322.16 (±0.04)
KI	903.09 (±0.01)	847.60 (±0.05)	570.66 (±0.04)	-566.71 (±0.04)	-514.93 (±0.07)	-259.11 (±0.07)

* Standard errors are given in parenthesis.

light of following aspects :

(i) Determination of apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}) from the density data as a function of the molar concentration of maltose in purely aqueous solutions and in the presence of alkali metal halides at temperatures in the range 293.15 to 313.15 K; (ii) Determination of the values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) or partial molar volume at infinite dilution (V_2^0) of maltose in purely aqueous solutions and in the presence of alkali metal halides viz., NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI at different temperatures; (iii) Determination of partial molar volumes of transfer ($V_{2,tr}^0$) of maltose from water to aqueous solution of alkali metal halides at different temperatures; (iv) Analysis of viscosity data of alkali metal halides in purely aqueous solutions and in the presence of maltose at different temperatures, by applying Jones-Dole equation¹² and (v) Ascertaining the structure-making and structure-breaking capacities of alkali metal halides in purely aqueous solutions and in the presence of maltose from temperature dependence of V_{ϕ}^0 .

Results and discussion

The concentration variation of apparent molar volume is

very useful for understanding the interactions in the present system. The variation of apparent molar volume with molar concentration is expressed by Masson's equation⁸,

$$V_{\phi} = V_{\phi}^0 + S_v \sqrt{c} \quad (1)$$

where V_{ϕ} is the limiting apparent molar volume and is equal to the partial molar volume at infinite dilution (V_2^0) and S_v is the experimental slope.

Studies on viscosity of ionic solutions are of great help in characterizing the structure properties of solutions. Various types of interactions exist between the ions in solutions and of these ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions are of current interest in all the branches of chemistry. These interactions help in better understanding of the nature of solute and the solvent i.e. whether the solute modifies or distorts the structure of solvent.

The nature of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions in a system involving electrolytes can be studied by applying Jones-Dole equation¹²,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + Ac^{1/2} + Bc \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or } \left[\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right] = Ac^{1/2} + Bc \quad (3)$$

$$\text{or } \left[\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right] = A + B\sqrt{c} \quad (4)$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and solvent, respectively. $\eta_{rel} = (\eta/\eta_0)$, is the relative viscosity of the system. c is the molar concentration of solution. A and B are the constants characteristic of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions^{13,14} respectively.

The values of V_ϕ for maltose in purely aqueous solutions and in the presence of NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI (0.10 and

0.50 M) at different temperatures have been determined as a function of the molar concentration.

The values of V_ϕ^0 and slope S_V of maltose in purely aqueous solutions and in the presence of NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI at different temperatures (293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K) were obtained from the plots of ϕ_v versus \sqrt{c} (Typical Figs. 1-6) and presented in Table 1.

A perusal of the Table 1 reveals that the values of V_ϕ^0 are positive and large and become increasingly smaller in the presence of increasing concentration of aqueous solution of NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI. Since V_ϕ^0 is a measure of solute-solvent interactions¹⁵ it follows that positive and large values

Table 2. Partial molar volumes of transfer at infinite dilution $V_{2,tr}^0$ of maltose from water to aqueous alkali halide solutions at different temperatures

Alkali halide	$V_{2,tr}^0$ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)					
	[Alkali halide] (mol dm ⁻³)			[Alkali halide] (mol dm ⁻³)		
	0.10			0.50		
	293.15	303.15	313.15 K	293.15	303.15	313.15 K
NaCl	-19.57	-26.80	-102.57	-113.06	-123.89	-113.79
KCl	-47.65	-20.59	-3.35	-120.92	-162.38	-111.32
KBr	-60.95	-42.26	-44.56	-245.79	-261.00	-258.45
KI	-69.38	-77.33	-55.49	-332.82	-360.70	-332.43

Table 3. Values of constants A and B of Jones-Dole equation for alkali halides in aqueous solutions of maltose at different temperatures*

Alkali halide	A (dm ^{3/2} /mol ^{-1/2})			B (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)		
	[Maltose] (mol dm ⁻³)			[Maltose] (mol dm ⁻³)		
	0.0	0.10	0.50	0.0	0.10	0.50
Temp. 293.15 K						
NaCl	0.0879 (±0.001)	-0.3889 (±0.001)	0.1426 (±0.002)	-0.0724 (±0.002)	0.4211 (±0.008)	-0.0356 (±0.001)
KCl	0.1338 (±0.002)	-0.3007 (±0.002)	0.0678 (±0.001)	-0.0860 (±0.001)	0.1273 (±0.003)	-0.0089 (±0.002)
KBr	0.1062 (±0.001)	-0.3116 (±0.001)	0.0267 (±0.001)	-0.0992 (±0.001)	0.1364 (±0.004)	-0.0799 (±0.001)
KI	0.0316 (±0.001)	-0.3590 (±0.001)	0.0730 (±0.001)	-0.0183 (±0.002)	0.1535 (±0.002)	-0.0138 (±0.002)
Temp. 303.15 K						
NaCl	0.1468 (±0.004)	-0.2528 (±0.002)	0.1743 (±0.002)	-0.0542 (±0.001)	0.3749 (±0.004)	-0.1844 (±0.001)
KCl	0.2328 (±0.003)	-0.2382 (±0.002)	0.1116 (±0.004)	-0.1608 (±0.004)	0.1188 (±0.002)	-0.0074 (±0.001)
KBr	0.1360 (±0.002)	-0.2247 (±0.001)	0.0958 (±0.003)	-0.0903 (±0.002)	0.1076 (±0.003)	-0.1074 (±0.001)
KI	0.1035 (±0.002)	0.0879 (±0.002)	0.1101 (±0.004)	-0.0674 (±0.003)	0.1124 (±0.002)	-0.0037 (±0.001)
Temp. 313.15 K						
NaCl	0.0512 (±0.001)	-0.3295 (±0.001)	0.0833 (±0.001)	-0.1144 (±0.001)	0.3926 (±0.004)	-0.1225 (±0.003)
KCl	0.1277 (±0.003)	-0.2715 (±0.004)	0.0980 (±0.002)	-0.0919 (±0.001)	0.1204 (±0.001)	-0.0284 (±0.002)
KBr	0.1360 (±0.004)	-0.2247 (±0.003)	0.0958 (±0.001)	-0.0903 (±0.001)	0.1076 (±0.003)	-0.1074 (±0.001)
KI	0.0766 (±0.001)	-0.3112 (±0.001)	0.0980 (±0.002)	-0.0383 (±0.001)	0.1422 (±0.002)	-0.0284 (±0.000)

* Standard errors are given in parenthesis.

Fig. 1. Variation of V_ϕ with \sqrt{c} for aqueous solution of maltose at 293.15 K.

Fig. 2. Variation of V_ϕ with \sqrt{c} for aqueous solution of maltose at 303.15 K.

Fig. 3. Variation of V_ϕ with \sqrt{c} for aqueous solution of maltose at 313.15 K.

Fig. 4. Variation of V_ϕ with \sqrt{c} for maltose in aqueous NaCl (0.1 M) at 293.15 K.

Fig. 5. Variation of V_ϕ with \sqrt{c} for maltose in aqueous NaCl (0.1 M) at 303.15 K.

Fig. 6. Variation of V_ϕ with \sqrt{c} for maltose in aqueous NaCl (0.1 M) at 313.15 K.

of V_ϕ^0 of maltose in purely aqueous medium indicate the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions, the intensity of which gets decreased in the presence of increasing concentration of aqueous solutions of NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI.

From the perusal of the values of S_v (vide Table 1) it is seen that these are negative and large in purely aqueous solution of maltose but are rendered less negative in the presence of increasing concentrations of aqueous solution of NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI. Since S_v is a measure of solute-solute interactions¹¹, a negative value of S_v reveals the existence of weak solute-solute interactions in purely aqueous solution of maltose and that the intensity of the interaction tends to become stronger in the presence of increasing concentration of aqueous solutions of NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI.

The partial molar volume of transfer at infinite dilution ($V_{2,tr}^0$) of maltose from water to aqueous NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI solutions has been estimated as below :

$$V_{2,tr}^0 = V_2^0 (\text{in aqueous NaCl/KCl/KBr/KI}) - V_2^0 (\text{in water})$$

The values for $V_{2,tr}^0$ have been summarized in Table 2. It is seen that the values are negative which decrease with the increase in the concentration of co-solutes (NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI).

The nature of $V_{2,tr}^0$ can be explained by invoking cosphere overlap model developed by Gurney¹⁶. The properties of water molecules in the hydration cosphere depend on the nature of solute species^{17,18}. According to this model when the solute molecules approach each other, their hydration cospheres overlap and some of the cosphere material is displaced resulting in a change in the thermodynamic parameters^{19,20}. NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI all exist in the ionic form and thus overlap comes into play because of the following types of interactions occur between solute (maltose) and co-solute (NaCl/KCl/KBr/KI) :

- (i) Interactions between the ions of co-solute (NaCl/KCl/KBr/KI) and hydrophilic-OH sites of maltose.
- (ii) Interactions between the ions of NaCl/KCl/KBr/I and hydrophobic parts/groups of maltose.

Table 4. Value of limiting apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}^l) and experimental slope (S_v) of alkali halides in aqueous solutions of maltose at different temperatures*

Alkali Halide	V_{ϕ}^l (cm ³ mol ⁻¹) [Maltose] (mol dm ⁻³)			S_v (cm ³ dm ^{1/2} /mol ^{-3/2}) [Maltose] (mol dm ⁻³)		
	0.0	0.10	0.50	0.0	0.10	0.50
Temp. 293.15 K						
NaCl	-513.46 (±0.04)	144.88 (±0.02)	429.71 (±0.09)	344.07 (±0.03)	-113.69 (±0.01)	-239.70 (±0.05)
KCl	-499.67 (±0.03)	326.99 (±0.01)	241.52 (±0.08)	343.29 (±0.01)	-190.50 (±0.05)	-176.87 (±0.03)
KBr	-494.60 (±0.04)	371.52 (±0.08)	367.64 (±0.06)	340.34 (±0.06)	-190.52 (±0.08)	-206.68 (±0.02)
KI	-497.95 (±0.05)	333.29 (±0.01)	333.14 (±0.06)	349.14 (±0.06)	-177.10 (±0.05)	-176.87 (±0.03)
Temp. 303.15 K						
NaCl	-400.76 (±0.04)	151.12 (±0.08)	400.99 (±0.01)	253.51 (±0.04)	-117.90 (±0.05)	-247.82 (±0.08)
KCl	-401.71 (±0.04)	330.00 (±0.05)	245.91 (±0.04)	263.22 (±0.03)	-191.22 (±0.03)	-179.50 (±0.50)
KBr	-392.90 (±0.05)	374.65 (±0.05)	345.55 (±0.05)	257.66 (±0.04)	-191.22 (±0.03)	-190.35 (±0.05)
KI	-376.04 (±0.06)	344.62 (±0.08)	337.76 (±0.04)	250.98 (±0.02)	-184.39 (±0.00)	-179.50 (±0.05)
Temp. 313.15 K						
NaCl	-520.36 (±0.04)	143.43 (±0.02)	436.46 (±0.04)	351.22 (±0.03)	-112.60 (±0.05)	-245.00 (±0.05)
KCl	-510.24 (±0.00)	325.03 (±0.07)	239.23 (±0.07)	352.63 (±0.02)	-188.79 (±0.01)	-174.93 (±0.07)
KBr	-495.70 (±0.05)	370.11 (±0.04)	312.52 (±0.08)	341.90 (±0.05)	-180.30 (±0.20)	-163.30 (±0.20)
KI	-490.38 (±0.02)	339.94 (±0.06)	331.39 (±0.01)	344.80 (±0.05)	-180.30 (±0.05)	-174.93 (±0.07)

*Standard errors are given in parenthesis.

Table 5. Values of coefficients a_i for computerized least square representation of alkali halides in aqueous solutions of maltose (temperature dependence of V_{ϕ}^l)

Alkali halide	[Maltose] (mol dm ⁻³)			[Maltose] (mol dm ⁻³)			[Maltose] (mol dm ⁻³)		
	0.00	0.10	0.50	0.00	0.10	0.50	0.00	0.10	0.50
NaCl	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_0	a_1	a_2
NaCl	-107037.93	703.87245	-1.1615	-6227.7312	42.156295	-0.06965	29793.957	-194.25449	0.32095
KCl	-95123.57	625.445935	-1.03245	-3307.0932	24.09337	-0.0399	-4806.04	33.444205	-0.05535
KBr	-94343.898	619.88675	-1.0225	-3128.34	23.181105	-0.03835	-3845.8944	30.40861	-0.0547
KI	-109047.57	716.570375	-1.18125	-7112.7662	48.866815	-0.08005	-4685.6165	33.228685	-0.05495

The first type of interactions contribute positively whereas second type of interactions contribute negatively to $V_{2,tr}^0$ values^{16,19}. Therefore, presently obtained negative values of $V_{2,tr}^0$ for maltose in the presence of 0.10 and 0.50 M aqueous solutions of NaCl/KCl/KBr/KI indicate that ionic hydrophobic interactions are dominating over the ionic hydrophilic interactions.

Viscosities of alkali metal halides (NaCl/KCl/KBr/KI) in purely aqueous solutions and in the presence of 0.10 and 0.50 M maltose solutions have been determined as a function of the concentration of alkali metal halides at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. The viscosity data have been ana-

lyzed by Jones-Dole equation (eq. 4). On plotting the quantity ($\eta_{rel.}$) vs \sqrt{c} straight lines are obtained (Typical Figs. 7–12). This is true in the absence/presence of maltose at different temperatures (293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K). The values of parameters A and B of Jones-Dole equation have been obtained from these linear plots and listed in Table 3. The constants A and B of Jones-Dole equation are specific for a solute-solvent system. Further, A is known as the Falkenhagen²¹ coefficient that takes into account ion-ion interactions and B is the Jones-Dole coefficient¹² that is related to ion-solvent interactions. A perusal of Table 3 shows that the values of A -coefficient are positive for all alkali halides in purely aqueous solutions which indicate the presence of strong ion-ion interactions over the concentration

Table 6. Limiting apparent molar expansibility (Φ_E^0) for various alkali halides in aqueous solutions of maltose at different temperatures

Alkali halide	Φ_E^0 [$\text{cm}^3 (\text{mol}^{-1}) (\text{K}^{-1})$]								
	[Maltose] (mol dm^{-3})			[Maltose] (mol dm^{-3})			[Maltose] (mol dm^{-3})		
	0.00			0.10			0.50		
	293.15	303.15	313.15 K	293.15	303.15	313.15 K	293.15	303.15	313.15 K
NaCl	22.8850	-0.3450	-23.5750	1.3205	-0.0725	-1.4655	6.0815	0.3375	-6.7565
KCl	20.1205	-0.5285	-21.1775	0.7000	-0.0980	-0.8960	0.9925	-0.1145	-1.2215
KBr	20.3950	-0.0550	-20.5050	0.6965	-0.0705	-0.8375	-1.6620	-2.7560	-3.8500
KI	24.0035	0.3785	-23.2465	1.9335	0.3325	-1.2685	1.0115	-0.0875	-1.1865

Fig. 7. Variation of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)\sqrt{c}$ with c for aqueous solution of NaCl at 293.15 K.

Fig. 8. Variation of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)\sqrt{c}$ with c for aqueous solution of NaCl at 303.15 K.

Fig. 9. Variation of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)\sqrt{c}$ with c for aqueous solution of NaCl at 313.15 K.

range 0.2 to 2.0 M. On the other hand, the values of B -coefficient are negative in purely aqueous solutions of these alkali halides. This shows the existence of weak ion-solvent interactions.

In the presence of 0.10 M maltose the values of A -coefficient are negative but change to positive as the concentration of maltose is increased to 0.50 M. On the other hand, the values of B -coefficient become positive in the presence of 0.10 M maltose but change to negative as the concentration of maltose is increased to 0.50 M. From this it follows

Fig. 10. Variation of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)\sqrt{c}$ with c for NaCl in aqueous maltose (0.1 M) at 293.15 K.

Fig. 11. Variation of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)\sqrt{c}$ with c for NaCl in aqueous maltose (0.1 M) at 303.15 K.

Fig. 12. Variation of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)\sqrt{c}$ with c for NaCl in aqueous maltose (0.1 M) at 313.15 K.

that in the presence of lower concentration of maltose ion-solvent interactions are rendered weak but become stronger at higher concentration of maltose. On the other hand, ion-solvent interactions become stronger at lower concentration of maltose but become weaker at higher concentration.

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of alkali halides have been determined as a function of their concentration in purely aqueous solutions as well as in the presence of 0.10 and 0.50 M maltose at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K.

Fig. 13. Variation of V_{ϕ} with \sqrt{c} for aqueous solution of NaCl at 293.15 K.

Fig. 14. Variation of V_{ϕ} with \sqrt{c} for aqueous solution of NaCl at 303.15 K.

Fig. 15. Variation of V_{ϕ} with \sqrt{c} for aqueous solution of NaCl at 313.15 K.

Fig. 16. Variation of V_{ϕ} with \sqrt{c} for NaCl in aqueous maltose (0.1 M) at 293.15 K.

Fig. 17. Variation of V_{ϕ} with \sqrt{c} for NaCl in aqueous maltose (0.1 M) at 303.15 K.

Fig. 18. Variation of V_{ϕ} with \sqrt{c} for NaCl in aqueous maltose (0.1 M) at 313.15 K.

From the plots of V_{ϕ} vs \sqrt{c} (Typical Figs. 13–18) the values of V_{ϕ}^0 and S_v have been obtained at different temperatures and presented in Table 4. A perusal of this Table shows that the values of V_{ϕ}^0 for all alkali halides are largely negative. This indicates the presence of very weak ion-solvent interactions. However, in the presence of maltose the values of V_{ϕ}^0 are rendered largely positive which shows that the ion-solvent interactions become stronger in the presence of maltose. This may be attributed²² to the decrease in electrostriction in the presence of maltose.

A perusal of Table 4 shows that the values of S_v are largely positive in purely aqueous solutions of alkali metal halides at different temperatures; but become largely negative in the presence of 0.10 and 0.50 M maltose. From this it follows that the ion-ion interactions which are strong in purely aqueous medium are rendered very weak in the presence of maltose solutions. This marked weakening of ion-ion interactions in the presence of maltose may be attributed to increased solvation in water + maltose mixed solvent system as compared to water alone.

The variation of V_{ϕ}^0 with temperature, of alkali metal halides in water follows the following polynomial equation⁷,

$$V_{\phi}^0 = a_0 + a_1T + a_2T^2 \quad (5)$$

over the temperature range under investigation. The values of coefficients a_i have been calculated by computerized least square method and listed in Table 5.

The partial molar expansibility Φ_E^0 has been calculated⁷ from the following equation,

$$\Phi_E^0 = \left[\frac{\partial V_{\phi}^0}{\partial T} \right]_P \quad (6)$$

The values of Φ_E^0 for various alkali metal halides in purely aqueous solutions and in the presence of maltose (0.0, 0.10 and 0.50 M) at different temperatures have been presented in Table 6.

Table 7. Values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ for alkali halides in aqueous solutions of maltose

Alkali halide	$(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$		
	[Maltose] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Maltose] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Maltose] (mol dm ⁻³)
	0.00	0.10	0.50
NaCl	-2.3230	-0.1393	-0.6419
KCl	-2.0649	-0.0798	-0.1107
KBr	-2.0450	-0.0767	-0.1094
KI	-2.3625	-0.1601	-0.1099

A perusal of Table 6 shows that Φ_E^0 decreases in magnitude with increase in temperature for the aqueous solutions of NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI indicating thereby that the behaviour of alkali metal halides is just like common salt^{23,24}.

It is also seen that in the presence of 0.10 and 0.50 M maltose solutions the values of Φ_E^0 also decrease with rise of temperature (vide Table 6).

Hepler⁹ has developed a technique of examining the sign of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ for various solutes in terms of long range structure-making and structure-breaking capacity of the solutes in aqueous solutions using the following general thermodynamic expression :

$$(\partial C_p/\partial T)_p = -T \left[\frac{\partial^2 V_\phi^0}{\partial T^2} \right]_p \quad (7)$$

On the basis of this expression it has been deduced that structure-making solute should have positive value, whereas structure-breaking solute negative value of the term $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$.

The values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ have been calculated using eq. (5) and listed in Table 7. It is seen that the values are negative in each case in water as well as in water + maltose mixed solvent systems. Thus, NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI behave as structure-breakers in these systems.

Experimental

Maltose (Ranbaxy, India) and alkali metal halides (NaCl, KCl, KBr and KI) (A.R., B.D.H.) were dried over P₂O₅ in a vacuum desiccator for more than 48 h. The reagents were always placed in the desiccator over P₂O₅ to keep them in dry atmosphere.

Freshly doubly distilled water (sp. cond. $\sim 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was used for preparing the solutions. An electronic balance having an accuracy of 1.0×10^{-4} g was used for the weight measurements.

The density was measured with the help of an apparatus similar to the one described by Ward and Millero²⁵ and followed by Parmar *et al.*^{22,26}. The viscosities of the solutions were measured at the desired temperature using an Ostwald's suspended level type viscometer as per details described by Findlay²⁷. Runs were repeated until three successive determinations were obtained within ± 0.1 s. Since all the flow times were greater than 100 second, the kinetic energy correction was not necessary²⁸.

The density and viscosity measurement were carried out in a thermostat bath, the temperature of which was controlled within ± 0.01 K.

References

1. M. Bastos, N. N. Volkoava and I. Wadso, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1993, **89**, 1351.
2. Vishnu, R. Wadhvani and Y. Akhtar, *Indian. J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 954.
3. F. Franks, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1987, **59**, 1189.
4. M. N. Gupta, *Biotechnol Appl. Biochem.*, 1991, **14**, 1.
5. K. Gekko and S. Koga, *J. Biochem. (Tokyo)*, 1983, **94**, 199.
6. T. S. Banipal, S. Sharma, B. S. Lark and P. K. Banipal, *Indian. J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 1106.
7. P. S. Nikam, A. B. Sawant, J. S. Aher and R. S. Khairnar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 197.
8. D. O. Masson, *Phil. Mag.*, 1929, **8**, 218.
9. L. G. Hepler, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1968, **47**, 4613.
10. T. S. Banipal, D. Kaur, G. Singh, B. S. Lark and P. K. Banipal, *Indian. J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 1131.
11. M. L. Parmar and D. K. Dhiman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 729.
12. G. Jones and M. Dole, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
13. J. M. McDowall and C. A. Vincent, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1974, **70**, 1862.
14. M. R. J. Dack, K. J. Bird and A. J. Parker, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, **28**, 955.
15. M. L. Parmar and S. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 592.
16. R. W. Gurney, "Ionic Processes in Solution". McGraw Hill, New York, 1953.
17. H. L. Friedman and C. V. Krishnan, *J. Sol. Chem.*, 1973, **2**, 37.
18. F. Franks, M. Pedley and D. S. Reid, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1976, **72**, 359.
19. J. E. Desnoyers, M. Arel, G. Perron and C. Jolicoeur, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 3346.
20. A. K. Mishra and J. C. Ahluwalia, *Int. J. Peptide Protein Res.*, 1983, **21**, 322.
21. H. Falkenhagen and E. L. Verman, *Z. Phys.*, 1932, **33**, 140.

22. M. L. Parmar and D. K. Dhiman, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1161.
23. F. J. Millero and W. D. Hansen, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 1758.
24. F. J. Millero, *Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 147.
25. G. K. Ward and F. J. Millero, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1974, **3**, 417.
26. M. L. Parmar and S. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 202.
27. A. Findlay, "Practical Physical Chemistry", ed. J. A. Kitchner, 8th ed., 1954, 70.
28. M. L. Parmar, D. K. Dhiman and R. C. Thakur, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 2032.